

Title of the Paper:**Sustainable Practices in the Steel Industry: A CSR Perspective**

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Abstract

In today's globalized world, Corporate social responsibility (CSR) is one of the great challenges faced by firms. As stakeholders require a lot more from companies than merely pursuing growth and profitability, So CSR has come a long way in India and other emerging markets. From responsive activities to sustainable initiatives, Corporate have clearly exhibited their ability to make a significant difference in the society and improve the overall quality of life. This paper focuses on the concept of CSR, its dimensions and relevance in emerging markets with special reference to Steel Industries in India. The concept Corporate Social Responsibility(CSR) refers to voluntary self regulation adopted by firms to improve aspects of the company that can relate to labour, environmental and human rights issues.

Key Words: Corporate social responsibility, Cultural, Sustainability, Stakeholders, Welfare etc.

Introduction

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is the continuing commitment for improving the quality of life of the workforce along with local community and society at large as it behave ethically and contribute to economic development. It is the persistent commitment of the business firm for social and economic development of communities. It is a tool that offers significant perceived benefits for the organization as it is done in many different aspects ranging from education, sanitation, development activities ,blood donation etc. Corporate Social Responsibility activities focusing on environmental factors, education, health care, cultural and peripheral development, family welfare, social initiatives etc. The bottom line in the realm of Corporate Social Responsibility is to engage and connect with people. It is one of the aspects to gauge the success of a firm as it shows how much is revert back to the society by the organization . It has been accepted as an ongoing activity as it helps them to attain a positive brand image, improve their customer's perception and increase customer loyalty, build strong stakeholder connection and contribute towards the global goals. It gives both practical and theoretical contribution towards the development in relate to long supply chain, broadening of consumer base and social and environmental demands etc. CSR means the activities done or taken by the corporate for the aim of the welfare of the society and sustainable development states that the resources should be effectively and efficiently utilized and can be saved for the future generation. CSR gives both practical and theoretical contribution towards development. CSR not only promotes economic development but also improves the quality of life and standard of living. After globalization the practices of CSR has came up with the new dimension to operate in the current world.

Obstacles in implementing CSR activities

- Measuring and reporting on CSR performance
- Defining the scope and goals of CSR
- Engaging and aligning with stakeholders
- Adapting to the changing CSR landscape
- Integrating CSR into the core business strategy
- Balancing the costs and benefits of CSR

Top CSR Trends in 2024-25

- ✓ Digital transformation and CSR software.
- ✓ Employee engagement.
- ✓ Thinking globally, acting local.
- ✓ Full supply chain accountability.
- ✓ Enhanced transparent reporting.

- ✓ Rapid response in times of crises.
- ✓ A focus for investment.
- ✓ Close focus on (SDGs) Sustainable Development Goals

The private as well as public sector organizations plays a important role in generating employment, profit earning as well as increasing the national income of the country. After various observations by the government of India it was decided that apart from all these things the organization or the undertaking should look after the needy people who are present the society.

So, the concept of Corporate Social Responsibility is been emerged. Through CSR, the company gives something to the society which the government has made mandatory for the organization. CSR is an effective way of maintaining and achieving sound business management. By caring out effective social responsibility, a company can frame or enhance its own value or the brand image in the eyes of the society. While using the resources of the society organization are accountable and answerable towards the stakeholders such as investors, employees, consumers, local residents etc.

Literature Review

Michael Porter and Mark Keramer (2002) finds that in case of philanthropy, executives increasingly see themselves as caught entities demanding even higher level of CSR and investors applying pressure to minimize short term profits. In relate to this philanthropy used as a form of public relations or advertising and promoting a company's image through high profile sponsorships. Corporations can use their charitable efforts to improve the competitive content i.e. the quality of the business environment. Using philanthropy to enhance competitive content aligns social and economic goals as well as improves a company's long-term business prospects. Adopting a content focused approach can make a company's philanthropic activities far more effective.

Nair and Sodhi (2012) observed that there are many SMEs engaged in socially relevant activities but the initiatives taken by them are not remarkable where as the CSR initiatives by the large sectors actually shows the impacts expected from India. So for this CSR framework within which SMEs and local authorities can effectively collaborate to promote wider socioeconomic objective and also address serious issues of environmental concerns.

According to Jayanta Bhattacharya (2012) CSR has not remain limited to societal welfare from the last 15 years but has grown together with a consistent business strategy to do well in both terms of business as well as receiving attention of the society. He has observed that CSR is vague in most of business operating in India which will cultivate as a

great form in the future not a philanthropy but more as an engine of empowerment of common people and creating sources of organizational growth.

A study by Sudhansu Kumar Das (2009) shows that companies dominating goals in not only maximization of profit as well as contribute to economic development through the community development. According to him, CSR is a concept that an enterprise is accountable for its impact to all the stakeholders. It is a continuous commitment by the business to contribute to economic development and improving the quality of living of the workforce. He further states that the CSR is a process that makes the business people aware of the impact of their works in the internal and external communities.

Moreover, as per Swain and Naik (2009) social responsibility is not new to our country. CSR is understood as the obligation of corporate houses to take actions which protect and improve the welfare of society as a whole along with their own interests. As per notifications of Govt. of Orissa in the year 2004, companies are expected to pay 5% of their profit for the development of health, education, communication, agriculture in a 50km radius area of the factory.

Giannakakos (2014) in his study aims to look into the relationship between corporate governance and financial characteristics and the level of CSR disclosure in the United States. Board meetings, the average age of board members, the presence of women on the board, the board size, chief executive officer duality, financial leverage, profitability, firm size, board composition, and board commitment to CSR are corporate governance and economic features.

Jain and Datta and Roy (2014) in his research investigates management students' awareness of and attitudes regarding corporate social responsibility (CSR). Students are viewed as future corporate executives, and businesses value their views on corporate social responsibility. Students can help companies to understand their responsibilities to a variety of stakeholders.

According to Dhanesh (2015) in his study was to present a more socio culturally informed explanation of the primary drivers of corporate social responsibility (CSR) in India than what is already available in debates. The findings revealed that participant understandings of CSR drivers in India simultaneously negotiated seemingly contradictory notions of moral and economic imperatives, in-depth conversations with business leaders and senior managers actively involved in shaping CSR in India. And the ancient Indian idea of dharma could be a possible theoretical framework within which these fundamental drivers of CSR in India could be further understood, building on past recommendations for culturally situating the study of CSR.

Aggarwal and Jha (2019) in their study observed that due to the varying institutional embedding of CSR activities, there are significant disparities in the focus and form of CSR among countries. This research aims to identify significant pressures driving CSR practices to explain them within the framework offered by institutional theory. It also aims to broaden theory by offering a conceptual model that connects institutional forces, CSR activities, business reputation and

financial performance in a developing country like India. The approach is based on Scott's institutional theory, linking CSR practices to regulative, normative, and cognitive forces.

The relationship between CSR and financial performance is mediated through reputation. For the first time, the authors have suggested an integrative model that will aid in understanding the causes and implications of CSR practises in a developing country within a theoretical framework.

Need of the study

CSR play vital role within a globalizing World because CSR matching corporate operations with stakeholder values and demands at a time. As CSR can be best described as a tool approach to business so companies should take people together with them to reach to ground level, seek ways for progress on the planet which is not only work for profit but also work for prosperity of the community.

Objectives

1. To examine the impact of CSR on organizational performance.
2. To analyze the impact of CSR on organizational culture.
3. To examine the impact and its influence on CSR on corporate reputation.

Methodology

The study is based on the primary data. Primary data is collected through a structured questionnaire. The structured questionnaire is given to the selected sample from the population. A sample of 150 respondents is selected through stratified random sampling. Collected data is analyzed by using appropriate mathematical and statistical tools including percentage and Chi-Square test. And from records, circulars, leaflets, magazines of Rourkela Steel Plant, secondary data were collected.

Results and Discussion

1. Demographic Factors

The demographic factors of employees includes age, qualification ,years of experience.

Table 1.1: Age of the employees

Age	Number of Respondents	Percentage(%)
Less than 25	80	53.33
26 to 35 years	40	26.67
36 and above	30	20
Total	150	100

Source: Primary Data

Out of 150 sample respondents surveyed, 53.33% are less than 25 years, 26.67% are 26 to 35 years of age and remaining 20% are above 36 years.

Table 1.2: Qualification of the employees

Qualification	Number of Respondents	Percentage(%)
Diploma	76	50.67
Degree	42	28
P.G & others	32	21.33
Total	150	100

Source: Primary Data

Out of 150 sample respondents surveyed, 50.67% has done Diploma ,28% has Degree and remaining 21.33% has done P.G and above.

Table 1.3: Experience of the employees

Experience	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1-2 years	62	41.33
2-4 years	58	38.67
Above 4 years	30	20
Total	150	100

Source: Primary Data

Out of 150 sample respondents surveyed, 41.33% of respondents have 1-2 years experience, 38.67% have 2-4 years and remaining 20% of the respondents have more than 4 years of experience in the organization.

However, in relate to the above said objectives, the following hypothesis as enlisted for analysis and calculating of their validity

2. Impact of CSR on organizational performance

Table 2.1: Employee attitude in relate to organisational performance

Sl. No	Response/Attitude	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Strongly Agree	37	24.66
2	Agree	53	35.33
3	Neutral	22	14.67
4	Disagree	22	14.67
5	Strongly Disagree	16	10.67
	Total	150	100

Source: Primary Data

The data in the above table indicates that, 24.66 percent of respondents strongly agreed, 35.33 percent of respondents agree, 14.67 percent of respondents are neutral, 14.67 percent of

respondents disagree and remaining 10.67 percent of respondents strongly disagree about impact of CSR on organizational performance.

Hypothesis

H₀: CSR and organizational performance are independent

H₁: CSR and organizational performance are dependent

Table 2.2: Employee attitude in relate to organisational performance

Observed Frequency (O _i)	Expected Frequency (E _i)	(O _i -E _i)	(O _i -E _i) ²	(O _i -E _i) ² /E _i
37	30	7	49	1.63
53	30	23	529	17.63
22	30	-8	64	2.13
22	30	-8	64	2.13
16	30	-14	196	6.53
			Total	30.05

The calculated value of Chi-Square = 28.185.

The critical value of Chi-Square for 4 degrees of freedom at 5% level of significance is 9.488. Since the calculated value Chi-Square is greater than the critical value i.e., 30.05 > 9.488. Hence, H₀ is rejected and H₁ is accepted.

Inference

CSR and organizational performance are dependent.

3. Impact of CSR on organizational culture

Table 3.1: Employee attitude on organisational culture

Sl. No	Opinion	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Strongly Agree	51	34
2	Agree	35	23.34
3	Neutral	25	16.66
4	Disagree	23	15.34
5	Strongly Disagree	16	10.66
	Total	150	100

Source: Primary Data

The data in the above table indicates that, 34 percent of respondents strongly agree, 23.34 percent of respondents agree, 16.66 percent of respondents are neutral, 15.34 percent of respondents disagree and remaining 10.66 percent of respondents strongly disagree about the impact of CSR on organizational culture.

Hypothesis**H₀**: CSR and organizational culture are independent**H₁**: CSR and organizational culture are dependent**Table 3.2: Employee attitude on organisational culture**

Observed Frequency (O _i)	Expected Frequency (E _i)	(O _i -E _i)	(O _i -E _i) ²	(O _i -E _i) ² /E _i
51	30	21	441	14.7
35	30	5	25	0.83
25	30	-5	25	0.83
23	30	-7	49	1.63
16	30	-14	196	6.53
			Total	24.52

The calculated value of Chi-Square = 24.52.

The critical value of Chi-Square at 4 degrees of freedom at 5% level of significance is 9.488.

Since the calculated value of Chi-Square is greater than the critical value i.e., 24.52 > 9.488.

Hence, H₀ is rejected and H₁ is accepted.

Inference

CSR and organizational culture are dependent.

4. Impact of CSR on corporate reputation and its influence**Table 4.1: Employee attitude on corporate reputation and its influence**

Sl. No	Opinion	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Strongly Agree	52	34.66
2	Agree	39	26
3	Neutral	19	12.67
4	Disagree	22	14.67
5	Strongly Disagree	18	12
	Total	150	100

Source: Primary Data

The data in the above table indicates that, 34.66 percent of respondents strongly agree, 26 percent of respondents agree, 12.67 percent of respondents are neutral, 14.67 percent of respondents disagree and remaining 12 percent of respondents strongly disagree about the impact of CSR on corporate reputation and its influence.

Hypothesis**H₀**: CSR and corporate reputation and its influence are independent**H₁**: CSR and corporate reputation and its influence are dependent

Table 4.2: Employee attitude on corporate reputation and its influence

Observed Frequency (O _i)	Expected Frequency (E _i)	(O _i -E _i)	(O _i -E _i) ²	(O _i -E _i) ² /E _i
52	30	22	484	16.14
39	30	9	81	2.8
19	30	-11	121	4.03
22	30	-8	64	2.13
18	30	-12	144	4.8
			Total	29.9

The calculated value of Chi-Square = 29.9.

The critical value of Chi-Square at 4 degrees of freedom at 5% level of significance is 9.488.

Since the calculated value of Chi-Square is greater than the critical value i.e., 29.9 > 9.488.

Hence, Hence, H₀ is rejected and H₁ is accepted.

Inference

CSR and corporate reputation and its influence are dependent.

Recommendations

- Organisations while taking up various CSR projects to meet the requirements of stake holders, have given priority to comply all the requirements under the provisions of environmental laws and companies act.
- Much attention is required to be paid by the social scientists, corporate bodies to make appropriate provision to align the CSR with addressing emerging issues and concern towards society that having a wider magnitude to the state and national level.
- Separate CSR fund from the main budget to avoid lapse of fund and ensure full utilisation of dedicated funds.
- Company has been providing sufficient funds and proper implementation set up with detailed CSR policy for execution of CSR activities effectively.
- Company should evaluate impact of CSR activities on the society which would help the company in future planning of CSR initiatives.

Conclusion

Corporate Social Responsibility and ethical decision-making go simultaneously for many businesses. The organization that make ethical decisions are also those that have good corporate responsibility and profitability .The current study finds out the perception of CSR is one of the important aspects that impacts commitment towards the development. CSR improves employee's perception of their company. Steel industry has empowered the

communities by laying the path on which the future generations will treat. Corporate Social Responsibility provides necessary skills and enabling employees to make a new trends.

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